

THE PLURILITERACIES BOARDGAME

Background: what's behind this game?

What if we told you that you can understand a language **without speaking it**? That although it may feel like a language across the world from yours, with different roots and a different alphabet, is completely incomprehensible, you may actually **understand it more than you think**? Avez-vous déjà entendu l'expression « c'est du chinois » pour parler de quelque chose d'incompréhensible, de compliqué, d'abscons ? En jouant à ce jeu, vous vous rendrez compte que, en réalité, vous pouvez comprendre le chinois...

This feeling of complete incomprehension towards a foreign language is, in many cases, psychological, in the sense that we tend to picture languages as completely isolated from one another. In reality, languages **share a rich history** with **similar roots, grammars, vocabulary and prosodic patterns**. Let's take an example that we all love: **chocolate** in English and in Spanish, **chocolat** in French, **Schokolade** in German, which might seem predictable... but did you know it's also **çikolata** in Turkish, **شكلات** (shokolat) in Farsi, **巧克力** (qiǎokèlì) in Mandarin Chinese, **шоколад** (shokolad) in Ukrainian, **chokleti** in Swahili? This means that you may be able to understand what a sentence is talking about in a completely different language than yours, once you identify similar words, phrases or intonation. Languages are not bubbles isolated from each other; learning a language is not about exploring a completely separate world than yours; **our world is much more interconnected than once thought**.

This board game is about understanding and linking different languages, in line with several innovative concepts. This includes **receptive multilingualism**, which is mutual comprehension while speaking different languages by hearing one language but responding in another, and **pluriliteracies**, the heart of our project, in which we see the world as interconnected: different **cultures**, different **languages**, different **modalities**, different **technologies**, all have links between them. Nowadays, it's essential to hone all of these skills to be able to interact and connect with people from various backgrounds in order to become **better global citizens**.

We take inspiration from Fanny Meunier's *Le Grand Livre des Musiques: A Miller's Tale*, a children's book using music as a meaningful metaphor for language. In it, Meunier describes a world where, although everyone is aware of the existence of many different instruments of all kinds, everyone listens to the violin, because it's easier, more accessible, and the only music sold in stores. Eventually, children realise it is possible to have a house full of different kinds of music that can coexist, creating a beautifully diverse ecosystem of music. A **diverse ecosystem of languages** is what we strive to reach with this board game: highlighting the beauty of each one and, most importantly, **realising how interconnected they all are**.

We hope you enjoy the game, que vous vous rendez compte des liens infinis entre les merveilleuses langues de notre monde, y que gracias a estos vínculos podréis apreciar un mundo plurilingüe e interconectado.

-Daria and Isabel

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Prêt.e à découvrir le merveilleux monde multilingue dans lequel nous vivons ?

In this board game you'll find 8 cards, each with a different picture, telling a story. The game can be played in two ways:

Are you playing with a group where everyone speaks different languages?

If the group with which you are playing is multilingual, meaning everyone, or several people, speaks several languages, you can:

1. Choose a designated person who speaks several languages.
2. Put the 8 cards in front of your group. Look at the drawings on the cards.
3. When you're ready to start the game, have the designated person choose a card in their head. They can look at the cards printed below instead of the ones used to play the game to not give away what card they have chosen. They then describe, in a few sentences in a foreign language, the chosen card.
4. The players listen and try to identify which card the designated person is describing. Once someone wants to make a guess, they can put their hand on the card they believe is the corresponding one. Every correct guess is a point.
6. The designated person can either keep describing cards in their selected language, or the players can switch so that the player who guessed correctly now becomes the designated player and describes a card of their choosing in a new language.
7. Keep playing until all 8 cards have been guessed correctly!

Do you want to test your understanding of languages from all around the world?

If you want to discover and explore languages you have no contact with, you can:

1. Put the 8 cards in front of your group. Look at the drawings on the cards.
2. When you're ready to start, a designated person in the group chooses one of the 8 cards, then scans the QR code on that card. A list of languages will appear – select one language for this card and play the recording.
3. The players listen to the recording and try to identify which card the recording is describing. Once someone wants to make a guess, they can put their hand on the card they believe is the corresponding one.
4. Then move on to the next card, scan its QR code, and choose whichever language you'd like for that one. You can pick a different language for every card!
4. Every correct guess is a point. Keep playing until all 8 cards have been guessed correctly! The player with the most points wins!

Easier version: If you are struggling to guess the cards based on the languages alone, the designated person can add some gestures while they're listening to the foreign language to facilitate the guessing.

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Want to discover new languages? Scan the QR codes for multilingual audio!

